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Theme 3: Space Techniques applied to environmental monitoring and research
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Environmental monitoring of refugee camps using high-resolution satellite images

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Final Report

Project partners:

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)
Satellus
Infocarto

Norway
Sweden
Spain

Associated partner:

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Investigators:

Ola M. Johannessen (co-ordinator), Øyvind Dalen, Einar Bjørgo, Torbjörn Rost, Jean-Yves Bouchardy, Mohammed Babikr, Gidske Andersen, Sara Paulson, Anna Haglund, Carlos Ordoñez, and Stein Sandven

www.enviref.org

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<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)</p> <p>Edv. Griegsvei 3a N-5059 BERGEN NORWAY</p>	<p>Satellus</p> <p>(Metria Miljöanalys from 01.01.2001)</p> <p>Box 355 101 27 Stockholm SWEDEN</p>	<p>Infocarto</p> <p>C./ Chile, 10. Edificio, Madrid 92, Local nº 128 28290 Las Rozas SPAIN</p>	<p>United Nations High Commissioner for refugees (UNHCR)</p> <p>The Mapping Unit Case postale 2500 CH-1211 Geneve 2 Depot SWITZERLAND</p>
<p>Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50 dalen@nersc.no www.nrsc.no</p>	<p>Phone: +46 8 579 972 70 Fax: +46 8 579 972 80 torbjorn.rost@lm.se www.satellus.se</p>	<p>Phone: +34916301381 Fax: +34916307050 infocarto@infocarto.es www.infocarto.es</p>	<p>Phone: +41 227397963 Fax: +47 227397374 bouchard@unhcr.ch www.unhcr.ch</p>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of ENVIREF was *to develop and evaluate new products from high-resolution satellite imagery for application and exploitation in humanitarian relief operations.*

The project had the following sub-objectives:

- *To document the relief agencies requirements for geographic information in humanitarian relief-operations*
- *To improve existing and develop new methods and products based on high-resolution satellite imagery fulfilling the relief agencies geographic information requirements*
- *To validate, demonstrate and evaluate the new and improved products and methods based on high-resolution satellite imagery*
- *To evaluate the cost and benefits of using high-resolution satellite imagery in humanitarian relief operations*

ENVIREF has been co-ordinated by the **Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center** (Norway), with **Satellus** (Sweden), **Infocarto** (Spain) and the **United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)** (Switzerland) as project-partners.

The aim of ENVIREF was to investigate the use of geographic information derived from high-resolution satellite imagery for achieving more efficient and cost-effective planning and management of refugee camps. The project has benefited from close co-operation with major relief-organisations, including *International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)*, *Medecines sans Frontieres (MsF)*, *Oxfam UK*, *Norwegian Peoples Aid (NPA)*, and *Food for the Hungry International (FHI)*. Focusing on actual needs for geographic information in humanitarian relief work developed products included high-quality space maps of refugee camps, and associated roads, water resources, forest and vegetation.

MAIN TASKS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

BACKGROUND

Over the last years the world has seen many disasters in which large amounts of people have died due to limited efficiency of relief-operations, e.g. in Ethiopia, Rwanda, Burundi, Zaire, and the Sudan. When refugee camps are established, they are often located randomly where the refugees have gathered. This might cause high stress on the surrounding environment, which might not be able to provide e.g. firewood and water for the suffering people over a longer period of time. The average refugee camp lasts for approximately seven years, although there are those that last much longer.

Geographic information is in general a key factor in the decision-making procedures of humanitarian relief-operations. During humanitarian relief operations it is essential to rapidly collect as reliable and up-to-date information as possible for the region of interest.

The use of satellite images to support management of refugee camps is an innovative approach. Except for the Mapping Unit at UNHCR, humanitarian relief organisations have little experience with this technology. Due to the lack of experience, personnel working in the field might have difficulties interpreting the images and utilise the detailed information. Thus it is not obvious in this community that the use of satellite imagery can be beneficial, both

technically and economically. It has been our challenge to demonstrate that satellite imagery can be a valuable information source for fulfilling certain geographic information needs, especially when existing maps are out of date, unreliable or difficult to obtain.

THE RELIEF ORGANISATIONS REQUIREMENTS FOR GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Relief organisations requirements for geographic information was investigated and documented at a workshop organised at the beginning of the project. Several major relief organisations participated, including the UNHCR, the IFRC, NPA and MsF. The meeting revealed that there is a strong demand for geographic information in humanitarian relief operations. The price and time frame for receiving the data were said to be the most critical factors for not using satellite remote sensing imagery today. The most important information requirements and acceptable delivery time were:

- Infrastructure overview, including travelling distances, type and status of the major access roads, and land-use for camp site selection and logistics, 1-14 days
- Land-ownership, 1-7 days
- Water resources (ground water, lakes, rivers, indicators of water resources), 1-2 weeks
- Co-ordination maps (which organisations are involved and where), 1 week
- Landmines, 2-3 weeks
- Camp infrastructure, 3-4 weeks
- Agriculture (development, extent, soil, crops and livestock, refugee vs. local farming), 1-2 months
- Environmental aspects such as forest, tree species and deforestation, vegetation species, soil, quality of bio-mass, and water pollution, 2-12 months

It is important to note that all this information cannot be derived from satellite imagery, e.g. land-ownership and landmines. But, use of satellite data can contribute to fast, cost-efficient and objective information on many parameters in the above list, especially in areas where existing maps are of low quality or difficult to obtain. Technically, there is a contradiction between large spatial coverage and high spatial resolution. Therefore use of several types of satellite sensors in combination are needed for obtaining the required information at appropriate mapping scales. This means that satellite sensors with spatial resolution from 10-30m such as LANDSAT and SPOT, are useful for mapping the camp area surroundings, i.e. at scales of 1:40,000 and lower. For detailed mapping at scale 1:10,000 and higher of e.g. tents, buildings and camp infrastructure it is necessary to use very-high spatial resolution satellites such as IKONOS.

During the workshop the following case study areas were selected for the project:

- 1) 12 refugee camps at five different locations in Albania and Macedonia, Europe
- 2) 5 refugee camps in the south-eastern part of Nepal, Asia
- 3) 2 neighbouring refugee camps in the eastern part of Kenya, Africa,

Each area representing different climatic, environmental and refugee related conditions.

IMPROVE EXISTING AND DEVELOP NEW PRODUCTS AND METHODS

Data from high-resolution satellite sensors (spatial resolution from 6 to 30m) such as LANDSAT TM/ETM+, SPOT, and IRS-1D were used for producing maps of *infrastructure*, *water resources* and *vegetation cover* at an overview level ranging from scale 1:15.000 to

1:250.000. Images from these sensors can be used to accurately measure the location and extent of a refugee camp, although the spatial resolution is not good enough to reveal any details within a camp area, e.g. to monitor refugee hosting shelters, buildings, roads, etc.

A map over all surface water resources in the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region was produced by superimposing vector-data for all rivers and lakes on top of a low-resolution Digital Terrain Model (DTM). All water bodies were extracted from an LANDSAT-5 TM scene from September 1997. The various catchment boundaries and flow direction of the rivers was determined through careful analysis of the satellite image and the DTM in a GIS.

Vegetation cover mapping has been performed both with and without ground truth data. Without such information (from field surveys or existing vegetation maps) only very general assumptions can be made, such as e.g. delineation of forest/non-forest areas. These general maps can on the other hand be prepared very quickly, and be used to plan more in-depth field surveys. Taking advantage of Albania forest inventory maps (prepared and kindly provided by the UN Food and Agriculture Organisation) 3 detailed vegetation cover maps from the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region were made, showing among others the distribution of various vegetation and forest types in the region.

Very high-resolution satellite images from the IKONOS satellite (1m and 4m) were used to perform mapping of details such as roads, footpaths, separate buildings, tents, and water sites inside refugee camp areas in Nepal and Kenya. IKONOS is the first satellite to provide very-high resolution satellite imagery on the commercial market. An especially important result of the IKONOS-data analysis is the identification of single shelters, huts and buildings inside the refugee camp areas. For the investigated camp settlement in Nepal close to 100% of all present huts and buildings were identified and could be counted in the image. Such information can among others be used to make better estimates of the number of people living in a camp, which is needed to determine the amount of food and medicine needed. IKONOS images can also be used to support detailed planning of refugee camps, including expansions, and assessments of environmental changes in the immediate surroundings.

DEMONSTRATION AND EVALUATION WORKSHOP

In January 2001 a selection of the ENVIREF-products were presented to representatives from major relief organisations at a workshop specially organised by the ENVIREF team at UNHCR's location in Geneva. This meeting raised important awareness on how satellite remote sensing imagery can be used as information source to support the planning and management of larger humanitarian relief operations.

COST/BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Relevant and up-to-date geographic information is of key importance for refugee assisting operations. When assessing how such information can be obtained, also lower-cost methods, e.g. existing maps or GPS field data collection should be considered. If additional detailed spatial information is needed, especially over a wider region or in an area with rapid and recent developments, satellite imagery can be a good source of information.

In relation to environmental monitoring of refugee camps, there is no simple answer as to when the benefit of satellite imagery weighs up for the financial costs. The potential benefits vs. costs must be assessed on a case-by-case basis; sometimes the investment in satellite imagery can be justified - sometimes not.

Very high-resolution satellite imagery is in most cases preferable to aerial photography, both from a cost and benefit perspective, especially for smaller-area coverage such as refugee camps.

PROJECT DISSEMINATION

The project and main results have been presented at a number of international remote sensing related conferences, as well as several in several international workshops and forums regarding use and needs for geographic information in humanitarian relief operations.

A continuously updated web-site has been running throughout the project, presenting all related news, background information, products, reports, conference presentations, etc. All documents and products have been available for download at no cost.

During the project the following promotion material have been made:

- A leaflet describing the project and some of the products that has been prepared
- An atlas describing the main results of the project, including three data analysis examples and eight maps, all printed in A3-form.

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

The decision whether or not to invest in satellite imagery depends on what geographic information is already locally available, budgetary constraints, and the required time frame for when information is needed. For most applications, satellite imagery can provide information more quickly than aerial surveys, unless planes and pilots are already available locally.

Very high-resolution satellite imagery is in most cases preferable to aerial photography, both from a cost and benefit perspective, especially for smaller-area coverage such as refugee camps. However, if low-cost paper copies of aerial photographs can be obtained, e.g. through a local university or company, these can also serve as a useful purpose.

The most important aspect of the IKONOS data is the possibility to accurately reveal small details only a few meters wide in areas restricted from aerial surveys, or where such observations are very expensive. The high spatial resolution makes it possible to perform detailed interpretation of e.g. infrastructure and settlements without use of field observations. The high spatial accuracy of the localisation of the image makes it possible to verify and eventually to correct position of features reported in the field.

Under favourable conditions knowing the number of tents present can be used to make rough estimates of the number of people residing within the camp area. During the Enviref project counting the number of tents and small houses inside the Beldangi refugee settlements in Nepal, and the Dagahaley and Ifo refugee settlements in Kenya has been done successfully using very-high resolution images from the IKONOS satellite. This number has then been used to estimate the approximate amount of affected people living in the camp. Thus, the use of very high-resolution satellite images may be a significant contribution towards better estimates of the number of people affected during the first stages of a crisis. Aided by detailed field registrations from the camps we have also been able to delineate other important details within the camp, such as larger buildings hosting hospitals, schools, administration, police etc, in addition to water sites and wells, petrol pumps, and roads and

footpaths of various size. IKONOS images also have the potential to be used for detailed refugee camp planning and assessments of environmental changes.

Medium resolution (5-30m) satellite remote sensing images can provide much of the information needed by the relief agencies, but not always within the required time frame. To get a thematic overview of a region, e.g. major infrastructure, brief vegetation cover and potential water resources, images also a few years old often can be used. Given the mission goal of the LANDSAT-7 programme to acquire and periodically update a global archive of daytime, substantially cloud-free images of all land areas of the world, this sensor could become a particular valuable data source for the relief community in the coming years.

We find that by providing fast access to general thematic information over a larger region the LANDSAT-7 ETM+ sensor could be a valuable data source for the relief community, also due to both the global data archive and the low price of only USD600 pr. image.

For performing more detailed analysis, which is especially needed at a later stage of a crisis situation, images at a resolution available e.g. from the IKONOS sensor is needed.

Strategy and recommendation for future use is summarised in the following table:

Satellite	Parameters ¹	Benefits	Limitations
LANDSAT TM	Vegetation cover, surface water	Large spatial coverage, high spectral resolution (7 bands), large archive	Low spatial resolution, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
LANDSAT ETM+	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Large spatial coverage, high spectral coverage (7 bands), panchromatic band (15m resolution), low data price (USD600), large archive, liberal copyright regulations allow for important sharing of the data	Low spatial resolution beside the panchromatic band
SPOT XS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	High spatial resolution, medium spatial coverage	Low spectral resolution, expensive data, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
IRS-1D	Surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Medium to high spatial resolution	Low radiometric resolution (low contrast), copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
ERS SAR	Camp location, settlements, digital elevation data	Operates independent of clouds and light, quite low data price	Difficult to interpret, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
IKONOS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, residences	Very high spatial resolution, medium high spectral resolution	Small spatial coverage, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing

¹Without additional data such as e.g. existing maps or field observations only brief descriptions can be made regarding the vegetation cover. Detailed field registrations are also needed for identifying the various types of houses and buildings within a refugee camp area.

Table 1. Strategy and recommendation for future use.

1 MANAGEMENT PART

1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT WORKTASKS AND DELIVERABLES

The research work was divided into seven tasks with the following deliverables:

Task no.	Title	Task leader	Deliverables
1000 1100 1200 1300	Project management Overall project management Web-site management Data management	NERSC NERSC Infocarto NERSC	Final Report, including CDROM
2000 2100 2200	Identify customer requirements Workshop I Document customers' EO requirements	NERSC NERSC UNHCR	Project Report I: Customer requirements
3000 3100 3200	Improve existing and develop new products and methods Improve existing products and methods Develop new products and methods	NERSC NERSC Satellus	Project Report II: Improve existing and develop new products and methods
4000 4100 4200	Customer demonstration and evaluation Workshop II Post-workshop evaluation by customers	Satellus Satellus UNHCR	Project Report III: Demonstration and evaluation workshop report
5000¹	Refining improved and new products and methods	NERSC	Part of Project Report II and Final Report
6000	Cost/benefit analysis	UNHCR	Project Report IV: Cost-benefit analysis for the use of high resolution satellite imagery in refugee operations
7000	Product exploitation	Infocarto	Colourful leaflet, Atlas ² , included in Final Report

¹This task has been running in parallel with Task 3000, by continuously improving the products according to suggestions and comments from a.o. UNHCR field staff. In addition some examples of GIS-analysis, which was requested at the User Demonstration Workshop, are included in the Final Report.

²It has been decided to produce an image Atlas instead of a poster as the project partners believe such a product will receive more interest within the relief community. In this manner, more products can be shown as well.

1.2 PROJECT PARTNERS AND THEIR RESPONSIBILITY

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) was responsible for the overall project management, with Ola M. Johannessen as project co-ordinator. NERSC was task leader for Task 1, Task 2, Task 3, and Task 5, as well as for the overall exploitation of results in Task 7. In addition, NERSC was involved in organising the first workshop and collecting the customer requirements, develop products from high-resolution satellites, vegetation and hydrology studies, presentation of high-resolution products at the user demonstration workshop, and project presentation at international conferences and meetings.

Satellus was task leader for Task 4, and was involved in organising the user requirements workshop, develop products based on very high-resolution satellites (IKONOS), presentation of very high-resolution products at the user demonstration workshop, conclude the user evaluation, and GIS-analysis for refined products. From 01.01.2001 Satellus is part of Metria Miljöanalys at the National Land Survey of Sweden.

Infocarto was task leader for Task 7 and the web-site management in Task 1. Infocarto was involved in developing Digital Elevation Models (DTM) using interferometric SAR, applications of DTM-data, presentation of DTM-products at the user demonstration workshop, and production of project promotion material (leaflet, atlas).

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) task leader for Task 6, and was also involved in defining the user requirements, commenting on developed products throughout the project, organising the user demonstration workshop, cost/benefit analysis and project presentation at international conferences and meetings.

In order to gain interest among potential users a reference group was initiated during the project, consisting of the *International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)*, *Medecins sans Frontieres (MsF)*, *Oxfam UK*, *Norwegian Peoples Aid (NPA)*, and *Food for the Hungry International*. In addition to participating in the two workshops organised by the project, the reference group members received all products and reports, and provided comments and suggestions for improvements and refinements.

1.3 DISCREPANCY FROM ORIGINAL WORK PROGRAM

An important part of the project was to investigate the use and potential of very high-resolution satellite imagery for detailed mapping of refugee camps. At the project kick-off no such satellites were in orbit, but several were scheduled for launch within the year. Due to the failure with the launch of the first IKONOS satellite in summer 1999 very high-resolution satellite imagery were not available before the second IKONOS satellite was successfully launched on September 24, 1999. Although image acquisitions were officially available for the general public from January 1, 2000, we did not successfully receive our order until the middle of May. For this reason a six-month extension of the project was consented by the EC.

1.4 PROJECT MEETINGS

The following meetings were arranged during the project:

Kick-off meeting – 14-15.01.1999, at NERSC, Bergen, Norway:

Participants: NERSC: *Bjørge, E., Dalen, Ø., Johannessen, O.M.* – Satellus: *Rost, T., Pålsson, S.* – Infocarto: *Perez, E.* – UNHCR: *Bouchardy, J-Y.* – EC/CEO: *Hawkins, A.*

User requirements workshop – 8-9.04.1999, at Satellus, Stockholm, Sweden

Participants: NERSC: *Bjørge, E., Dalen, Ø.* – Satellus: *Rost, T., Pålsson, S., Olson, B., Wester, K., Rosengren, M., Anderson, C.* – Infocarto – *Yague, A.*, – UNHCR: *Bouchardy, J-Y.* – EC/CEO: *Hawkins, A.* – IFRC: *Mohagheh, M.* – NPA: *Holte, I.*

1st progress meeting – 2-3.09.1999, at NERSC, Bergen, Norway:

Participants: NERSC: *Bjørge, E., Dalen, Ø.* – Satellus: *Rost, T.*, – Infocarto: *Mazarro, L. d. C.* – UNHCR: *Bouchardy, J-Y.* – EC: *Businaro, T.*

2nd progress meeting – 3-4.06.2000, at Satellus, Stockholm, Sweden:

Participants: NERSC: *Dalen, Ø.* – Satellus: *Rost, T., Haglund, A.* – UNHCR: *Bjørge, E.*

User workshop + Final meeting – 17-19.01.2001, at UNHCR, Geneva, Switzerland

Participants: NERSC: *Dalen, Ø., Sandven, S.* – Satellus: *Rost, T., Pålsson, S.* – Infocarto: *Ordoñez, C.* – UNHCR: *Bouchardy, J-Y., Bjørge, E.* + about 20 persons from various relief organisations for the workshop

1.5 DISSEMINATION

The project has been presented in both the mass media, and at a number of international conferences, meetings, and workshops. See detailed description below.

Popular Science Articles

Aiding Refugee Relief, by Einar Bjorgo, Space Imaging Notes, November-December 1999. See: www.imagingnotes.com/novdec99/nd99diff.htm#aiding
 Very High Resolution Satellites: A New Source of Information in Humanitarian Relief Operations, by Einar Bjorgo, American Society for Information Science (ASIS) Bulletin, October 1999. See: www.asis.org/Bulletin/Oct-99/bjorgo.html

Newspaper and internet articles

LeMonde Diplomatique April 2001: Des millions de refugies, un fardeau pour le Sud (in French, but also translated into other languages), by Philippe Rekacewicz
 Satellites Find A Home For the Homeless, by Daniel Sorid. See www.space.com/scienceastronomy/planetearth/enviref_990923.html.
 Towards a New Humanitarian Technology: The ENVIREF Project. Environmental Monitoring of Refugee Camps using High-Resolution Satellite Images. To be published in an online magazine by The Genocide Prevention Center.

Presentations at major conferences

- 28th Symp. on Remote Sensing of Environment, Cape Town, South Africa, on March 27-31, 1999. Project presentation by Lasse Pettersson and Øyvind Dalen, NERSC.
- ESA ERS-Envisat Symp., Gothenburg, Sweden, 16-20 Oct. 2000. Project presented by Øyvind Dalen, NERSC.
- Global Disaster Information Network (GDIN) conferences 2000 (Hawaii and Istanbul) and 2001 (Canberra), presentations by Jean-Yves Bouchardy, UNHCR.
- EURISY Conference on The Use of Satellites and Integrated Technologies for Humanitarian Purposes, Varese, Italy, 19-20 September 2000, keynote presentation by Jean-Yves Bouchardy, UNHCR.
- EURISY Conference on The Use of Satellites and Integrated Technologies for Humanitarian Purposes, Varese, Italy, 19-20 September 2000, Project presentation by Ola M. Johannessen and Øyvind Dalen, NERSC.
- United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) conference poster exhibit, New York, July 2000, by Jean-Yves Bouchardy, UNHCR.
- ESRI User Conference 2000 - Merging GIS tools with humanitarian relief requirements - lessons learned and the way forward, by Jean-Yves Bouchardy and Einar Bjorgo, UNHCR.
- UN Office for Outer Space Affairs Twenty-First Session of the Inter-Agency Meeting on Outer Space Activities, Vienna, Austria, 22-24 January 2001, presentation by Jean-Yves Bouchardy, UNHCR.
- Swedish Mapping days 1999, Jönköping, Sweden. Project presentation by Torbjörn Rost, Satellus.
- GIT 2001, Geographic IT, 2001, Stockholm, Sweden. Project presentation by Torbjörn Rost, Satellus.

Major UNHCR presentations/training

- Lecture to the Universities of Geneva and Lyon (Architecture) regarding GIS applied within Humanitarian operations, by Jean-Yves Bouchardy
- UNHCR Workshop on Emergency Management trainings 2000 and 2001
- ENVIREF-example included in UNHCR-internal Operations Learning Programme

Presentation of results in upcoming publications

- United Aid from the Sky - A Framework Paper on Current and Potential Use of Satellite Imagery in United Nations Humanitarian Organizations, by Einar Bjorgo. To be published by US Institute of Peace
- UNHCR manual on the use of satellite imagery for UNHCR's operations
- Brochure on UNHCR Geographic Information and Mapping Unit (GIMU) activities
- Project summary paper to be submitted to an international remote sensing journal

Presentation of results at upcoming conferences

- Earth Observation for Environmental Monitoring, Security and Humanitarian Aid, Zurich, Swiss Space Agency, 28 August
- UN Geneva-based GIS users, Coordination Meeting, 21 September 2001
- Eurisy Conference on Peace-Building from Space: Use of satellite technologies for post-crisis development, 17-18 December 2001

Links to ENVIREF from selected key websites

- ReliefWeb: www.reliefweb.org
- GDIN: www.gdin.org
- CBS News Disaster Links:
www.cbsnews.com/network/htdocs/digitaldan/disaster/disasters.htm
- Federation of American Scientists (FAS): www.fas.org/eye/methods2.htm
- Global Emergency Management System: www.disasters.org/emgold/Library/GEMS.htm
- Humanitarian Resource Institute: smamedia.wdnetwork.com/hri/idin/

Other

Book chapter in Commercial Observation Satellites - At the Leading Edge of Global Transparency, John C. Baker, Kevin M. O'Connell and Ray A. Williamson (Eds.), RAND corporation.

1.6 FINANCIAL SUMMARY

The project has been completed within the budget frame, as listed in the following table:

	NERSC	Satellus	Infocarto	UNHCR	Total
EC-funding	146.5	92.5	76	45	360
Own funding	146.5	92.5	76	45	360
Total	293	185	152	90	720

Table 1.1. Budget for each partner in the ENVIREF-project. All figures in kECU.

2 INTRODUCTION TO THE SCIENTIFIC PART

Over the last years the world has seen many disasters in which large amounts of people have died due to limited efficiency of relief-operations, e.g. in Ethiopia, Rwanda, Burundi, Zaire, and the Sudan. When refugee camps are established, they are often located randomly where the refugees have gathered. This might cause high stress on the surrounding environment, which might not be able to provide e.g. firewood and water for the suffering people over a long period of time. The average refugee camp lasts for approximately seven years, although there are those that last much longer.

Geographic information is in general a key factor in the decision-making procedures of humanitarian relief-operations. During humanitarian relief operations it is essential to rapidly collect as reliable and up-to-date information as possible for the region of interest.

The use of satellite images to support management of refugee camps is an innovative approach. Except for the Mapping Unit at UNHCR humanitarian relief organisations have really no experience with this kind of technology. Further, due to lack of experience personnel working in the field can have difficulties interpreting the images in order to derive the information they are seeking. For this reason it is not obvious in this community that the use of satellite data could be beneficial, both technically and economically. It has thus been our challenge in the project to demonstrate that satellite imagery can be a valuable information source for fulfilling certain geographic information needs, especially when existing maps are out of date, unreliable or difficult to obtain.

3 CASE STUDY AREAS

The data acquisitions and analysis in the ENVIREF-project has been carried out for three different locations with significant refugee population, representing various climatic and natural environments. The choice of locations were made together with the reference group, based on criteria such as involvement by relief organisations, available satellite acquisitions, and access to other environmental data that could be used in the analysis. The *Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia* border region is part of the Mediterranean climate belt. The area is characterised by a rich bio-diversity, and rapidly increasing development and industrialisation, often at the expense of local environmental conditions. Located beneath the Himalayan mountain massif the study area in eastern *Nepal* has a semi-tropical climate. The area is partly threatened by erosion, due to among others deforestation and extensive cultivation. The camps in *Kenya* are located in a semi-arid area with relatively fragile natural resources and low rates of biomass growth.

3.1 KOSOVO-ALBANIA-MACEDONIA BORDER REGION

As a consequence of the war in Kosovo during spring 1999 several refugee camps were established in the border region of Albania and Macedonia for Kosovo-Albanians that had to flee from their country. Our study concerned altogether 12 camps at 5 different locations close to the villages Bojane, Neprosteni, Senokos and Radusa in Macedonia, and seven camps around Kukes, Albania. Major parts of this region are relatively mountainous, and include a.o. a large mountain massif separating Albania from Kosovo and Macedonia. The Albanian region is dominated by mining industry, and contains mainly forest and more or less abandoned agricultural fields as well as some villages and smaller settlements. The Macedonia region constitutes mainly a very large agricultural area, in addition to several villages and settlements of various sizes.

Satellite data acquired for the study included a LANDSAT-5 scene from September 1997, an IRS1-D panchromatic scene from May 27 1999, three ERS SAR PRI scenes from respectively August 4 1997, May 31 1999 and August 9 1999, as well as 26 ERS SAR SLC-images from 1995-96 (for producing a Digital Elevation Model of the region using the SAR interferometry technique). UNHCR and USAID provided digital vector data of the refugee camp locations, roads, rivers, lakes, borders, and geographic places at a scale of 1:200,000 and 1:1,000,000. This data served as support to the image interpretation and production of the space-maps. Albanian forest inventory maps prepared and provided by the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the UN, Italy has been used in the analysis for the preparation of vegetation cover maps from the satellite images.

More information about the Kosovo-refugee programme can e.g. be found at:

<http://www.unhcr.ch/world/euro/seo/kosovo.htm>

Figure 3.1. *Satellite data coverage for the Kosovo-border region case study*

3.2 SOUTH-EASTERN NEPAL

In the Jhapa and Morang districts in the eastern Nepal there are five refugee camps hosting some 90,000 Bhutanese refugees. Compared to most refugee camps Beldangi, Goldhap, Khudunabari, Timai and Sarishare are all rather small, which has been a conscious policy of the Nepalese government. The major influx of the refugees occurred from 1990 to 1993, and all camps still exist today. In the area more than 70% of the total land area has been cultivated, and the remaining forest resources occupy 10% and 16% of the land area of

respectively Jhapa and Morang. Deforestation is considered the most serious threat arising from the presence of the refugees, the population influx adding to the existing pressure on the local forest resources, though no formal study on the impacts of refugee firewood gathering has been carried out [UNHCR, 1998]. In some cases the land now occupied by the refugee camps had already suffered from previous human interference and were already in degraded or bare condition. Nevertheless, further impacts have arisen from the camp establishment due to e.g. clearing of unstable trees and ground level vegetation for building houses at safe locations [UNHCR, 1998]. To minimise the reduction in forest-cover several reforestation projects have been successfully applied in e.g. the Beldangi camps. Some of the camps are threatened by flooding during the monsoon season.

The satellite data obtained for this area are shown in Figure 3.2, and include a LANDSAT-7 ETM+ scene of November 6 1999, two SPOT XS scenes of respectively February 16 1989 and January 5 1992, two ERS SAR scenes of respectively June 21 1992 and May 15 1996, and one IKONOS scene from May 2000 (Pan+MS). In addition we have received topographic paper-maps covering all refugee settlements at a scale of 1:25,000, made by the Survey Dep. of Nepal. These maps are based on aerial photographs acquired in 1992, and were verified in the field in 1996.

More information about the refugee situation in Nepal can e.g. be found at:

<http://www.unhcr.ch/world/asia/nepal.htm>

Figure 3.2. Coverage of the satellite data obtained for the Nepal case study area.

3.3 NORTH-EASTERN KENYA

In the North-eastern Kenya two refugee camps have been analysed. The refugee camps in the Dadaab region are located at three different locations – Dagahaley, Ifo and Hagadera. Dadaab is located in the Garissa district, some 110-km east of Garissa town in the northeastern province of Kenya. The Garissa district is an arid and semi-arid zone with a fragile ecosystem. The existing vegetation is shrubby savannah with a domination of the acacias. The agricultural potentials are extremely low, close to non-existent. The average annual rainfall varies from 150 to 300mm. Potential annual-average evaporation oscillates between 2,100 and 2,500mm. It is a hot to very hot zone, with an average annual temperature between 24 and 30°C. The maximum temperature lie between 30 and 36°C and the minimum between 18 and 24°C. The three camps were established between 1991 and 1992. 95% of the refugees come from Somalia and the reminder comes from Ethiopia, Sudan and Uganda. The male-female ratio is roughly equal, with children making up 50% of the population, which has grown from 4,000 to 15,000 during the existence of the camps. The local people congregate near the camps in order to trade with the refugees [UNCHR, 1998].

For this study one IKONOS scene 11 by 11km, covering both the Ifo and Dagahaley camps was obtained, see Figure 3.3. The scene includes both the panchromatic and multispectral bands, and was acquired on respectively May 26 and May 25, 2000. Two images, i.e. a merge of panchromatic and multi-spectral data, were made. No supplementing data were of such quality that it could be used for the interpretation and analysis.

More information about the refugee situation in Kenya can e.g. be found at: <http://www.unhcr.ch/world/afri/kenya.htm>

Figure 3.3. Location of the IKONOS image acquired over the study area in Kenya.

4 GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS

Geographic information is in general a key factor in the decision-making procedures of humanitarian relief-operations. Most operations can be divided into three phases, each with varying needs for geographic information. These phases are *emergency*, *care and maintenance*, and *repatriation*. During an emergency it is essential to rapidly collect information for the region of interest. In this respect, maps are one of the main information sources. These are used to disseminate baseline information on e.g. the location of refugees, road networks, and possible water sites in the area. During the care and maintenance phase humanitarian agencies seek updated information on the number of refugees needing assistance, as well as refugee population density, while for the repatriation phase information on the environmental conditions on the refugees' area of origin is needed. In this respect information on available land for sustainable agricultural schemes are of vital importance. Also possible longer-term environmental impacts need to be addressed in this phase.

Various needs and requirements for geographic information in humanitarian relief operations was collected and discussed at a dedicated workshop in Stockholm April 1999. Unfortunately, due to the crisis in Kosovo, Oxfam and several national agencies had to cancel their participation just two days before the workshop. The following relief agencies contributed to the geographic information requirement survey:

- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)
- International Federation for the Red Cross and Red Crescent Society (IFRC)
- Norwegian Peoples Aid (NPA)
- Medecins sans Frontieres (MSF)

A questionnaire addressing current use and needs for geographic information in humanitarian relief operations were distributed to the participants prior to the workshop as a basis for the discussions. It is important to note that the workshop addressed the need for geographic information in general, thus the survey also include information that obviously cannot be derived from satellite imagery. In summary the most important information requirement and acceptable delivery time were:

- Infrastructure overview, including travelling distances, type and status of the major access roads, and land-use for camp site selection and logistics, 1-14 days
- Land-ownership, 1-7 days
- Water resources (ground water, lakes, rivers, indicators of water resources), 1-2 weeks
- Co-ordination maps (which organisations are involved and where), 1 week
- Landmines, 2-3 weeks
- Camp infrastructure, 3-4 weeks
- Agriculture (development, extent, soil, crops and livestock, refugee vs. local farming), 1-2 months
- Environmental aspects such as forest, tree species and deforestation, vegetation species, soil, quality of bio-mass, and water pollution, 2-12 months

It should be noted that the requirements listed are general. The shifting environments and nature of the situations might lead to various needs for information. Some situations last for several years, while others are normalised within months. Thus, the time intervals listed may also vary from one operation to another.

Even though use of satellite imagery cannot meet all these requirements it provides a means for fast, cost-efficient and objective information on many parameters in the above list, especially in areas where existing maps are of low quality or difficult to obtain. Technically, there is a contradiction between large spatial coverage and high spatial resolution. Therefore use of several types of satellite sensors in combination are needed for obtaining the required information at appropriate mapping scales. This means that satellite sensors with spatial resolution from 10-30m such as LANDSAT and SPOT, are useful for mapping the camp area surroundings, i.e. at scales of 1:40,000 and lower. For detailed mapping at scale 1:10,000 and higher of e.g. tents, buildings and infrastructure it is necessary to use very-high spatial resolution satellites such as IKONOS.

5 NEW AND IMPROVED PRODUCTS AND METHODS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Common high-resolution earth observation satellites operate either in the optical (i.e. 0.3-14 μ m wavelength) or the microwave portion of the spectrum (i.e. 1mm-1m wavelength). The term optical is used because lenses and mirrors can be used to refract and reflect the observed energy, basically it is a combination of sun light reflected at the earth's surface and radiance from the earth that is observed by the optical sensors (i.e. visible to thermal range). This means that these sensors only can operate during sunlight, and that e.g. clouds, shadows and haze will obscure the signal received. Sometimes a combination of several images must be produced in order to obtain a useful view over a larger area or region. Use of multi-spectral sensors that register in different parts of the optical spectrum is particular valuable for discriminating different features on the ground, as the difference in the spectral signature curves for e.g. soil and vegetation vary as a function of the wavelength.

A high-resolution microwave radar sensor emits and receives its own energy and can thus operate independent of the daylight. Such sensors are also capable of penetrating the atmosphere under virtually all conditions. Depending on the wavelength used the radar waves can penetrate clouds, haze, shadows, light rain- and snowfall, and smoke. On the other hand microwave reflections bear no direct relationship to their counterparts in the visible and thermal range, and surfaces that e.g. appear rough in the visible range may be seen as smooth by the radar sensor. Radar-images can appear quite different from 'normal' views, and thus require a completely different interpretation approach.

Table 5.1 summarises the satellite sensors investigated in the project:

Sensor	Spectral bands	Spatial resolution [m]	Swath width [km]
IKONOS	1 pan ¹ + 4 ms ²	1/4	11
IRS-1 D	1 pan	5.8	63-70
SPOT XS	3 ms	20	60-80
LANDSAT ETM+	1 pan + 7 ms	15/30/60	185
LANDSAT TM	7 ms	30/120	185
ERS SAR	radar	25	100

¹Panchromatic ²Multispectral

Table 5.1. Characteristics of the satellite sensors investigated during the project

In view of the user requirements the investigated satellite sensors can provide information on infrastructure, water resources, vegetation and elevation, at scales ranging from 1:200,000 up to more than 1:10,000.

High resolution satellite sensors (spatial resolution from 6 to 30m) including LANDSAT TM/ETM+, SPOT, and IRS-1D has been used for producing maps of *infrastructure*, *water resources* and *vegetation cover* at an overview level ranging from scale 1:15.000 to 1:250.000. Images from all these sensors can be used to accurately measure the location and extent of a refugee camp, although the spatial resolution is not good enough to reveal any details within a camp area, e.g. to identify independent residences, roads, and so forth. These sensors can provide much of the information needed for managing humanitarian relief operations, but not always within the required time frame. To get a thematic overview of a region, e.g. major infrastructure, brief vegetation cover and potential water resources, images a few years old can often be used. Given the mission goal of the LANDSAT-7 programme to acquire and periodically update a global archive of daytime, substantially cloud-free images of all land areas of the world, this sensor could become a particular valuable data source for the relief community in the coming years. Add to this the low price of only USD600 pr. image and no copyright regulations for data and information sharing.

For performing more detailed analysis, which is especially needed at a later stage during a crisis situation, images at a resolution available e.g. from the IKONOS sensor is needed.

5.2 DETAILED CAMP MAPPING USING IKONOS

Camp Overview and *Detailed Infrastructure* maps for refugee camps in both Nepal (Beldangi) and Kenya (Ifo and Dagahaley) have been made from IKONOS scenes acquired during May 1999. The maps were prepared in the scale of 1:10,000, and show the camp and the major roads leading to the camp. They also show all other extracted features inside the different camps. The different infrastructure buildings are coloured by category, according to the legend. The surrounding civilian villages are labelled with their names. Also a so-called *Detailed Camp Infrastructure* map has been made from the IKONOS scenes and prepared for printing at a scale of 1:5,000. These show all minor roads within the camp, the infrastructure buildings in different colours depending on category and a dot for each camp hut. In addition, all refugee shelters have been counted for each camp. The various IKONOS-maps are shown in Figure 5.1 to Figure 5.4.

The corner co-ordinates provided by the data-provider Space Imaging were used for the initial orientation of the images. The rectification for the Beldangi case was further improved using a map at scale 1:25,000. No supporting information or maps were available for evaluating the interpretation of the images from Kenya. From experience the IKONOS provided corner co-ordinates have an absolute accuracy of about 10m. The mapping was performed by interpretation and onscreen digitising of the two different images produced (RGB image and NIR+RG image). The features that could be extracted from the images include major and minor roads, paths, rivers, river area, streams, camp huts, infrastructure, buildings, ferro-cement tanks, fences, camp borders and civil villages. To extract the camp huts both images were needed, to see which dots were huts and which were trees. Inside the camps there is a need for additional data about the infrastructure. Even though it is rather easy to extract objects such as buildings from the satellite images, it is quite impossible to tell if the buildings are schools or medical centres etc. Information from people working in the camp is important for the final result and also for acceptance of the product. Some features in Nepal, for example the police office, were located with the satellite image and identified with

a map. Other infrastructure buildings were located with the satellite image and identified with information from local relief staff.

The visual interpretation of the number of huts in the Beldangi refugee camps fits quite well with figures reported by the UNHCR-office in Kathmandu. From the image it was interpreted to be 44,100 huts while the official number is 44,556, i.e. the error is only about 1%. The difference in area can be due to the rules for measuring the camp size. In the interpretation the boundaries were set by the edge of the wood. From the image analysis the camp area was measured to be 125.5 ha, while the official area is 116.6 ha. This difference is mainly due to an unclear definition of the borders of the camp.

In Kenya the interpretation of shelters was more difficult, due that the shelters have the same shape as the surrounding bushes. The population in the refugee camps in Kenya was counted in a field survey in 1998, but only for some blocks. This survey shows, for Ifo 4488 inhabitants compared to 2818 interpreted, and for Dagahaley 4217 inhabitants compared to 3422 interpreted. Maybe the number of inhabitants has changed since 1998. The interpreted camp areas are too large compared to what has been reported by UNHCR. This is due to how narrow the boundary is set to the blocks, if no free space is included, which it is in the interpretation. This can be seen in the figures; 235.5 ha measured for Dagahaley and 327 ha interpreted, and for Ifo 290.9 ha measured compared to 417 ha interpreted.

5.3 CAMP LOCATION AND SURROUNDINGS MAPPING USING LANDSAT AND IRS

The camp location and surroundings-map from Kukes, Albania shown in Figure 5.5 is a combination of two sensor types, where the colour (thematic information) is from a LANDSAT TM image (30m) and the high spatial details (i.e. infrastructure and settlements) are from an IRS-1D image (6m). The map covers some 8*8km and shows all access roads from the nearby airport and the Kosovo-border located just north of the map, in addition to rivers and lakes. The upper left part of the map shows only the LANDSAT image and thus demonstrates the effect of different resolutions. Such maps could e.g. be used for more detailed route planning and logistics. Using data from the LANDSAT 7 satellite that carries the improved ETM+ sensor maps with nearly the same level of detail as the LANDSAT-IRS combination can be prepared. An example for the Beldangi camp settlement in Nepal is shown in Figure 5.6.

5.4 REGION OVERVIEW MAPPING USING LANDSAT

The overview map in Figure 5.7 from the Jhapa and Western-Morang district in Nepal covers some 20*16km, including two different camp locations. Superimposed on the map is the extent of the two camps, all access roads, the water resources in the region, and important geographical names. The map includes a legend for image interpretation, an overview map showing its position relative to international borders, a scale-bar and a north-arrow, in addition to some general cartographic information. The map was prepared using LANDSAT ETM+ data. Such maps could e.g. be used for route planning, and could also be used in a discussion concerning finding suitable locations for new camps. A similar map was prepared for the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region, based on a LANDSAT TM scene from September 1997 and various vector data such as camp locations, roads, rivers, geographical names, and refugee entry points, available at scale 1:250,000 and 1:1,000,000 provided by USAID. This map was made for printing at A1-paper and for this reason the details in the map are not justified if printed at A4.

Figure 5.1. Detailed camp overview map for the Beldangi camps in Nepal.

Beldangi, Nepal

Detailed Camp Infrastructure

Overview

Legend	Image Interpretation Legend
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beldangi I Beldangi II Extension cemetery Health facilities petrol pump police station school major roads paths river small roads stream camp border cemetery civil village ferro cement tanks health facilities large houses mechanical workshop offices/officers police station refugee women forum relief items distribution centers relief items storage centers river area school water collection sites water tower 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture area Bushes Forest Grass Camp huts Infrastructure Major roads Small roads Paths Stream Water tower

Beldangi camps - Nepal	
Camp I:	Area 505,800m ² Population: 18,300
Camp II extension:	Area 327,200m ² Population: 10,250
Scale:	1:50,000
Projection:	UTM zone 45
Origin:	27° 12' N
Scale factor:	0.9993
Data sources:	ROADS 2: Map 16-2006 © Space Imaging 2006
Topographic image © The Survey Dept of Nepal 1986	Map produced by ENVIREF 2014

Figure 5.2. Detailed camp infrastructure map for the Beldangi II and Ext. camps in Nepal.

Figure 5.3. Detailed camp overview map for the Dagahaley camp in Kenya.

Kukes - Albania Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure

Figure 5.5. Camp location and surroundings map for the Kukes region in Albania.

The Beldangi refugee settlements, Nepal
 Camp location and surroundings: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.6. Camp location and overview map for the Beldangi refugee camps in Nepal.

Morang and western Jhapa districts, Nepal
 Overview: Infrastructure and water resources

Figure 5.7. Overview map for the Morang and western Jhapa districts

5.5 WATER RESOURCE MAPPING

Both LANDSAT and SPOT imagery have been used to map the surface water situation over a wider region for both the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia and Nepal case study areas. Combined with digital elevation data also the river flow direction has been determined. Multi-temporal acquisitions by SPOT and LANDSAT over the same area in Nepal have been used to derive changes in the watercourse. Several changes were identified at the more level part of the region, while any eventual changes around the camps appeared to be too small to be detectable using data at this resolution.

For the water resources map from the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region (Figure 5.8) rivers and lakes have been extracted from the LANDSAT TM image and superimposed on a low resolution DTM (1*1km horizontal and ~500m vertical, available for the whole world free of charge from USGS). This map also includes the various catchment boundaries and flow direction of the rivers. Such maps could be especially important in areas with less water resources than this region.

5.6 VEGETATION COVER MAPPING

The purpose of a landuse classification is to generalise and attribute the satellite image into a few map features, like houses, forest and open land. Such a product can be used e.g. for statistical calculations like computing the expected wood availability or size of built-up areas. If several maps are created from multi-temporal image acquisitions potential landuse changes can be derived. A landuse map may be used as input to various GIS operations, e.g. finding areas at a certain distance from water. It can also be used as an objective document showing the state of one or several features at the time of image acquisition.

5.6.1 VEGETATION MAP PRODUCED FROM IKONOS

A landuse map for an area of about 30km around the Beldangi camps was prepared using the IKONOS scene of May 2000. A topographic map was used as reference data and for extracting a forest mask used for minimising the miss-classification between forest and tea-plantations. Mix-up between houses and some arable land also occurred. In order to separate them, a diversity map was generated. In this particular area there was a very distinct difference in heterogeneity between built-up areas and arable land. This fact was used to identify wrongly classified house and road pixels in homogeneous areas. Also objects already manually interpreted in the image was used for reference, such as:

- River areas and streams
- Roads and paths
- Official buildings (based on additional information)

Finally, all manually interpreted objects were superimposed on top of the classification result. Altogether 11 different classes were identified, and the result is shown in Figure 5.9.

Normally, when generating a landuse classification map a lot more detailed knowledge about the area of interest is needed. In this case, the only reference data available was a topographic map. Based on this fact it was not reasonable to divide the data into more than about 8 classes, that could be easily distinguished in the Ikonos image. The extra classes; paths, streams and official buildings were taken from previous manually interpretations.

A mix-up between the classes was expected and therefore great effort was put on finding methods for identifying erroneous classification results. At an early processing stage a diversity map proved to be valuable for separating open vegetated areas, which in most cases were very homogeneous, from built-up and road areas. This was further important for defining rules for which classes that were allowed to appear in a certain area. Nevertheless, except for visual assessments there are no measurements on how good the final result reflects the reality.

The only analysis that indicates the accuracy is an example of shelter estimation that was carried out based on the classification result. The number of shelters within the Beldangi I and Beldangi II camps was computed by dividing the total number of pixels allocated to the class 'House' on an expected average number of pixels per house. Compared to a manual counting of shelters (which in turn had an error of about 1% compared to official numbers given by the UNHCR office in Kathmandu) the result for the two camp areas differed by respectively 3% and 10%.

5.6.2 VEGETATION MAP PRODUCED FROM LANDSAT TM

Vegetation cover mapping using LANDSAT TM has been performed both with and without ground-truth information about the vegetation situation in the investigated areas. Analysis performed without such information can only be used to make general assumptions about the vegetation cover, such as separating vegetated and non-vegetated regions, e.g. the location and distribution of forest (without mentioning the type of wood). These maps can on the other hand be prepared very quickly, and also be used to plan where in-depth field observations should be collected. Having access to some kind of information about the vegetation in an area, e.g. through field observations or existing vegetation maps, more detailed maps can be prepared, showing e.g. the location of the various forest and vegetation types appearing in the region. This was done for the vegetation cover study in the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia region using forest classification maps from Albania.

The vegetation cover map from Kukes (supervised classification) was prepared based on Albanian forest inventory maps (training data), and shows areas of pasture, agriculture, settlements, and various forest types, see Figure 5.10.

5.6.3 SUMMARY

The result of the land cover classification indicates that it is quite easy to automatically map houses, roads, forest and water using IKONOS imagery. These classes may be very important when planning for a new camp, e.g. in terms of access to wood and water and existing infrastructure. It is more difficult to classify different types of arable land. This was just a small example of the possibilities over an already established camp area, while for real-case planning purposes a larger area should be mapped. A suggested workflow could be to start at smaller scales with classifications and analyses based on LANDSAT or SPOT data. Further on, when it comes to more detailed studies, large-scale mapping and analysis can be accomplished with IKONOS data.

Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region

Overview: Water resources and elevation

Figure 5.8. Water resources map for the Kosovo-Albania-Macedonia border region.

Figure 5.9. Landuse map for the Beldangi region, based on IKONOS imagery.

Kukës, Vegetation map

Figure 5.10. Detailed vegetation cover map for the Kukës region in Albania.

5.7 GIS-ANALYSIS

Only with a GIS-analysis tool all the information in a satellite image can be fully utilised. With the help of a GIS-program the determination of suitable camp location areas could be based on a DTM and various objects interpreted in a satellite image, such as river areas, civil villages and major roads. For a real-case computation of the best camp location many parameters have to be taken into account, sometimes also including political issues that that can be very difficult to parameterise. However, in this brief example for the Beldangi area in Nepal, only a subset of the environmental parameters of importance have been included:

- slope and aspect originating from the DEM
- distance to water, major roads and villages from the interpreted objects

The values and thresholds used are assumptions based on experience from the area. Additional information that would have been of interests include landuse, water quality, biomass quality, population, ethnicity, temperature, prevailing wind direction, minimum area etc. Thresholds and rules for computing the best camp locations from the available data were as follows:

Slope: < 7%

Aspect: SW - S - SE

Distance to water: 200-1500m

Distance to major roads < 500m

Not valid in existing civil villages

The result (see Figure 5.11) shows that the Beldangi I camp is partly settled in a non-suitable area. The reason for this is that part of the camp is closer to the river than the limit of 200m. In fact, there have been problems with water flooding in this camp, and embankments have been built in several places.

It should be noted that this is only a very brief example of a method that could be used for determining suitable areas. The limited data available and result shown is not valid for making any judgements about the location of these particular camps, nor must the result be seen as a critic on where these camps have been located.

5.8 CHANGE DETECTION ANALYSIS

5.8.1 INTRODUCTION

Changes in landuse, especially vegetation, can often be detected by comparing digital satellite images from different years or different dates. Digital satellite images can easily be used for detecting major changes in vegetation like clear cuts. While other types of changes can be more difficult to detect. Other changes cause only marginal reflectance response, and the natures of these are relatively unknown. Change detection tasks are of interest from a relief point of view to detect degradation of forest, new infrastructure, erosion and changes of land use.

When the aim is to detect changes in vegetation or land use using multitemporal remote sensing data, the first issue to consider is the spectral change caused by these changes and the factors that can affect to the separability of the changes. If the change of land use does not alter the intensities detected by the sensor, or the changes caused by disturbing factors obliterate the change, which are of interest, the remote sensing data is not useful.

The most evident and wide-area changes in the nature are caused by seasonal variation. Therefore, if possible images should be acquired in the same season, to avoid the intensity differences caused by the seasonal cycle. Vegetation should be in a relatively stable phase such as dry winter season or middle of growing season. Clouds are a factor that often rejects the possibility to choose the perfect registration date. The ideal case for change detection is if data exists from a similar or the same sensor and recorded in the same spatial resolution, viewing angle, spectral bands and time at day.

5.8.2 CALIBRATION

The purpose of the calibration has two objectives: to improve the separability of the change of interest, and make images radiometric comparable with each other. Method used is developed at Metria for forestry applications, which performs an image radiometric matching over a predefined area.

5.8.3 CHANGE DETECTION METHODS

There are two approaches of change detection: comparative analysis of classifications of images from different times and simultaneous analysis of multi-temporal images. There are several methods for simultaneous analysis:

- image rationing
- vegetation index differencing
- direct multi-date classification
- background subtraction
- thresholding
- image differencing
- image regression
- principal component analysis
- post-classification comparison

The methods applied for this analysis are image differencing and vegetation index differencing by NDVI. Image differencing is one of the most used methods in remote sensing. It's based on pixel by pixel basis and are done on corresponding band from different

times. NDVI is computed for two images acquired at different times. The NDVI is then subtracted and normalised. One advantage working with division of spectral wavelength bands is that it reduces the influence of topography, e.g. reduces the difference if the same type of vegetation appear at locations with different sun-conditions. In the same manner, the influence of varying soil moisture can be reduced.

5.8.4 INPUT DATA

Available input data has been:

Sensor	Registration date	Spatial resolution	Wavelength (nm)
SPOT XS registered	1992-01-05	20 meter	500 – 590 green 610 - 680 red 790 – 890 near IR
Ikonos MS	2000-05-18	4 meter	450 – 520 blue 520 – 600 green 630-690 red 760 – 900 near IR
Ikonos Pan	2000-05-16	1 meter	450 – 900 pan
Orthophoto	1999	1 meter	400 – 700 pan
Orthophoto	1989	1 meter	400 – 700 pan

Finnmap produces the orthophoto images. An orthophoto is an aerial image where has compensated for height distortion with a digital elevation model (DEM) and an image is made by a number images as a mosaic. All data has been geographically corrected to the same map projection.

5.8.5 ORTHOPHOTO VERSUS ORTHOPHOTO

The result of change detection between two orthophotos is difficult for several reasons. Firstly they are registered on different time of the day and probably different seasons so the most common changes that appear in the image are individual tree shadows. However major changes such as new roads (light ares) and former tracks (dark linear features) appear in the change image, see Figure 5.13. Changes as decreased vegetation appears light and an area that has been vegetated appears dark. The camp infrastructures are possible to detect only with some prior knowledge of the location. Changes in agricultural areas appear as significant due to its nature. The radiometric resolution is low as each image consists only of few grey levels. The input images are probably scanned analogue aerial photographs, see Figure 5.12.

5.8.6 ORTHOPHOTO VERSUS IKONOS

When comparing IKONOS panchromatic image data to orthophoto (See Figure 5.14), the use of satellite data improves the change studies significantly. This is mainly due to the narrow viewing angle of the satellite sensor, which a.o. minimises the shadows, in addition to the high radiometric resolution of IKONOS data. The result of the change detection analysis between the IKONOS image and the aerial orthophoto is shown in Figure 5.15. The camp infrastructure, for example, is clearly identified in the change image as well as other major changes.

Figure 5.12. *Left) Panchromatic orthophoto from 1989.
Right) Panchromatic orthophoto from 1999.*

Figure 5.13. *Result of change detection for the orthophotos from 1989 and 1999. Areas where the vegetation has disappeared appear light and areas that has become vegetated appear dark.*

Figure 5.14 left) Panchromatic orthophoto from 1989
right) Panchromatic IKONOS from 2000

Figure 5.15. Result of change detection analysis using IKONOS and Orthophoto (1989- 2000)

5.8.7 IKONOS VERSUS SPOT

Image differencing

When comparing SPOT XS to IKONOS MS imagery (see Figure 5.16) the approach is not obvious. Different geometric resolution must be handled, as well as the difference in the radiometric resolution. In this example the SPOT XS data was re-sampled to 4 meters resolution by cubic convolution. Individual spectral channels were then used in an image differencing analysis. The result of differencing using the red channels (see Figure 5.17) revealed the camp infrastructure, but not as good as when using data with higher spatial resolution. XX3 shows the result of the image differencing using the NIR bands. With this band some individual buildings are detected. More studies on semi-automatic change detection methods are in order to perform more reliable and recurrent change detection analysis on these kinds of data.

NDVI Normal Difference Vegetation Index

Change detection analysis using vegetation index differencing revealed some interesting results. The input data are shown in XX4. The camp infrastructure, including several buildings, can be clearly seen (XX5). Also major changes appear clearly.

This algorithm was also applied to a larger area around surrounding the Beldangi camps. XX6 reveals some significant changes in the river area and in the camp area. The Beldangi II & Ext. camp area can be clearly seen, while the northern part of Beldangi I is mixed with variations in the river area. This could be an indicator of flooding problems. As always arable land is difficult because of it's nature.

5.8.8 SUMMARY

The result and quality of a change detection analysis is highly dependent on the input data. Factors such as similar sensor characteristics and time of the year for the image acquisitions are important for the result. Radiometric differences, as well as spatial resolution must be taken into account. In the case of both different spatial and radiometric characteristics use of an intermediate resolution is recommended, i.e. a resolution comparable to the size of the objects to be detected.

Having data with different radiometric resolution the use of indexes, such as NDVI, seems to be a reliable alternative. The minor differences in the radiometric wavelengths are then reduced. The use of the same satellite sensor with registrations from the same vegetation phase, but from different years are optimal, but may not be possible in a operational and recurrent use of change detection for monitoring camp development.

Stratification approaches should be tested, as it will be much easier to follow areas where the basic location are known and the change detection studies can be focussed on the neighbourhood.

This small pilot study only intends to introduce the possibilities for change detection analysis using these kinds of data. More refinements and testing is needed for the method to be operational. The benefit of this kind of analysis is its objectiveness. Changes possible detected could be deforestation, camp extension, erosion, flooding, etc.

Figure 5.16. *left) SPOT XS from 1992-01-05
right) Ikonos MS from 2000-05-18*

Figure 5.17. *Image differencing using the red channel of SPOT and IKONOS 1992-2000)*

Figure 5.18. Image differencing using the near-infrared channel of SPOT and IKONOS 1992-2000

Figure 5.19. left) NDVI from SPOT 1992-01-05
right) NDVI from Ikonos 2000-05-18

Figure 5.20. *Result of change detection between SPOT and IKONOS using NDVI (1992-2000)*

Figure 5.21. *Result of change detection over a larger area between SPOT and IKONOS using NDVI (1992-2000)*

6 USER DEMONSTRATION WORKSHOP

A customer demonstration and evaluation workshop was held at UNHCRs locations in Geneva on January 18th 2001. The results of the ENVIREF project were presented to representatives from a number of humanitarian relief organisations. Questioning and discussions among the participants followed the presentations. At the workshop the following topics were presented:

- **User requirements:** Mr. Einar Bjorgo, UNHCR Geographic Information and Mapping Unit (GIMU), presented geographic information requirements as listed by relief organisations in the ENVIREF project. The presentation highlighted which requirements could be met using satellite imagery.
- **Geographic information and satellite imagery within the UNHCR:** Mr. Jean-Yves Bouchardy, Head UNHCR (GIMU) presented recent developments regarding the use of satellite imagery, Global Positioning Systems (GPS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) within UNHCR.
- **Financial aspects and limitations:** Mr. Einar Bjørgo presented financial aspects on the use of satellite imagery. Cost of data for main sensors was listed. Special focus was put on the cost per square km (for comparing sensors), information requirements, such as level of details required, and possibility for sharing data and derived information. Limitations of satellite imagery, in particular cost, cloud cover and copyright restrictions were highlighted. Special attention was drawn to the liberal copyrights (no restrictions for sharing raw data and derived information) and low cost (USD600/scene) for Landsat 7 data.
- **Camp infrastructure using Ikonos data:** Mr. Torbjörn Rost, Metria (Satellus) focused on camp infrastructure mapping using Ikonos data, with examples from the Beldangi camp settlements in South Eastern Nepal. Ikonos is the first commercial very high-resolution satellite (VHR) to provide data with a geometric resolution of 1 meter.
- **Camp overview and surroundings:** The focus of Mr. Øyvind Dalen's, NERSC, presentation was products prepared from the satellites LANDSAT, IRS and SPOT related to the camp overview and region overview level (i.e. a lower mapping scale than for the IKONOS-based products), in addition to water resources and vegetation cover maps. NERSC also presented some examples on how satellite imagery can be used for measuring changes in the vegetation cover in the vicinity of a refugee camp.
- **Use of elevation data in humanitarian relief operations:** Mr. Carlos Ordoñez, Infocarto, presented a description of how Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) may be of help in humanitarian relief operations. All the examples in the presentation are located in the surroundings of the Neprosteno refugee camp (Macedonia) and have been produced by using a DEM derived from ERS SAR interferometry.

During the presentations the participants raised several questions and made remarks both related to the products shown and to the use of satellite imagery in general. They concerned among others, the education level needed for using satellite derived products, the costs involved and how to use this kind of information in the field.

7 COST/BENEFIT ANALYSIS

7.1 BACKGROUND

The analysis is carried out in order to address costs and benefits for the use of high-resolution satellite imagery versus traditional methods, such as field surveys, standard maps and aerial photography, for environmental monitoring of refugee camps. As informed decisions require relevant information to be analysed, also some important issues in the context of refugee assistance has been addressed, as well as a background on the various methods available to collect geographic information relevant for refugee operations. Also the use of standard maps and aerial photos has been described. The terms “environment” and “environmental” are here used in a broad sense, also including parameters related to the surrounding geographic environment, e.g. hydrology, elevation and road network, in addition to e.g. changes in forest cover.

7.2 THE VALUE OF INFORMATION

According to Bounfour and Lambin (1999) the general concept of acquiring and using information can be seen as a method for reducing uncertainty. For relief agencies working in refugee situations, reducing uncertainty in operational planning and implementation is obviously of great importance. However, it is difficult to view information as a commodity *per se*, as it is by definition indivisible and difficult to appropriate (Arrow, 1971 and Murota, 1988). Furthermore, the real value of information is difficult to estimate until one actually receives it (Machlup, 1980). At the same time, the cost of not having the required information is difficult to estimate. Once information is collected the crucial part in taking advantage of it, is to ensure a proper analysis and understand the information correctly (Repo, 1989) - only then can decision-makers take full advantage of the information.

If useful information is missing and at the same time considered important enough, then one must decide how important the missing information is for the specific operation (and potential spin-off products such as use by local government at a later stage). Is the missing information of such importance that one should set aside a budget to acquire it? If so, which methods should be used to ensure a cost-effective approach for obtaining the information?

When narrowing the term “information” to geographic, spatial information, which is what is relevant for this assessment, one also narrows the way potential benefits and the related costs of the information can be addressed. When including field data, satellite images and derived products as part of a decision-making procedure, the objective should be to facilitate more intelligent decision-making, shortening the decision-making cycle, earlier implementation of decisions and more efficient resource management. However, to fully utilise the value of satellite imagery in the decision-making process, this should be included as part of a Geographic Information System (GIS), together with other relevant information, such as location of refugee camps, road network, international borders etc.

7.3 SUMMARY

- Relevant and up-to-date geographic information is of key importance for refugee assistance operations. When assessing how such information can be obtained, one should also consider lower-cost methods, e.g. existing maps or GPS field data collection.
- If additional detailed spatial information is needed, satellite imagery can be a good source of information, but the end-user should know exactly what type of information is

needed, and be informed about the limitations of satellite imagery prior to ordering scenes. Remotely sensed information should be verified by field data whenever possible, especially for land-classification products.

- Very high-resolution satellite imagery is in most cases preferable to aerial photography, both from a cost and benefit perspective, especially for smaller-area coverage such as refugee camps. However, if low-cost paper copies of aerial photographs can be obtained, e.g. through a local university or company, these can also serve a useful purpose.
- There is no simple answer as to when the benefit of satellite imagery weighs up for the cost of investing in this type of information in relation to environmental monitoring of refugee camps. The potential benefits vs. costs must be assessed on a case-by-case basis: sometimes the investment in satellite imagery can be justified - sometimes it can not.
- The decision whether or not to invest in remotely sensed imagery depends on what geographic information is already locally available, budgetary constraints, and the required time frame for when information is needed. For most applications, satellite imagery can provide information more quickly than aerial surveys, unless planes and pilots are already available locally.

8 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Geographic information is in general a key factor in the decision-making procedures of humanitarian relief-operations. During humanitarian relief operations it is essential to rapidly collect as reliable and up-to-date information as possible for the region of interest.

The aim of ENVIREF has been to investigate the use of geographic information derived from high-resolution satellite imagery for achieving more efficient and cost-effective planning and management of refugee camps. The project has benefited from close co-operation with major relief-organisations. By focusing on actual needs for geographic information in humanitarian relief work developed products included high-quality space maps of refugee camps, and associated roads, water resources, forest and vegetation.

The use of satellite images to support management of refugee camps is an innovative approach. Except for the Mapping Unit at UNHCR, humanitarian relief organisations have little experience with this technology. It has been our challenge to demonstrate that satellite imagery can be a valuable information source for fulfilling certain geographic information needs, especially when existing maps are out of date, unreliable or difficult to obtain.

Relief organisations requirements for geographic information was investigated and documented at a workshop organised at the beginning of the project. Several major relief organisations participated, including the UNHCR, the IFRC, NPA and MsF. The price and time frame for receiving the data were said to be the most critical factors for not using satellite imagery today.

Despite that all required information cannot be derived from satellite imagery (e.g. land-ownership and landmines), satellite imagery can contribute to fast, cost-efficient and objective information on many parameters, especially in areas where existing maps are of low quality or difficult to obtain. Further, use of several types of satellite sensors in combination might be needed for obtaining the required information at applicable mapping scales.

With each area representing different climatic, environmental and refugee related conditions, the following case study areas were selected for the project:

- 1) 12 refugee camps at five different locations in Albania and Macedonia, Europe
- 2) 5 refugee camps in the south-eastern part of Nepal, Asia
- 3) 2 neighbouring refugee camps in the eastern part of Kenya, Africa,

In January 2001 a selection of the ENVIREF-products were presented to representatives from major relief organisations at a workshop specially organised by the ENVIREF team at UNHCR's location in Geneva. This meeting raised important awareness on how satellite remote sensing imagery can be used as information source to support the planning and management of larger humanitarian relief operations.

Medium resolution (5-30m) satellite remote sensing images can provide much of the information needed by the relief agencies, but not always within the required time frame. To get a thematic overview of a region, e.g. major infrastructure, brief vegetation cover and potential water resources, images also a few years old often can be used. Given the mission goal of the LANDSAT-7 programme to acquire and periodically update a global archive of

daytime, substantially cloud-free images of all land areas of the world, this sensor could become a particular valuable data source for the relief community in the coming years.

The most important aspect of the IKONOS data is the possibility to accurately reveal small details only a few meters wide in areas restricted from aerial surveys, or where such observations are very expensive. The high spatial resolution makes it possible to perform detailed interpretation of e.g. infrastructure and settlements without use of field observations. The high spatial accuracy of the localisation of the image makes it possible to verify and eventually to correct position of features reported in the field.

Strategy and recommendation for future use is summarised in Table 8.1:

Satellite	Parameters ¹	Benefits	Limitations
LANDSAT TM	Vegetation cover, surface water	Large spatial coverage, high spectral resolution (7 bands), large archive	Low spatial resolution, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
LANDSAT ETM+	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Large spatial coverage, high spectral coverage (7 bands), panchromatic band (15m resolution), low data price (USD600), large archive, liberal copyright regulations allow for important sharing of the data	Low spatial resolution beside the panchromatic band
SPOT XS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	High spatial resolution, medium spatial coverage	Low spectral resolution, expensive data, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
IRS-1D	Surface water, infrastructure, camp location, settlements	Medium to high spatial resolution	Low radiometric resolution (low contrast), copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
ERS SAR	Camp location, settlements, digital elevation data	Operates independent of clouds and light, quite low data price	Difficult to interpret, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing
IKONOS	Vegetation cover, surface water, infrastructure, residences	Very high spatial resolution, medium high spectral resolution	Small spatial coverage, expensive data, copyright restrictions reduce possibility for data sharing

¹Without additional data such as e.g. existing maps or field observations only brief descriptions can be made regarding the vegetation cover. Detailed field registrations are also needed for identifying the various types of houses and buildings within a refugee camp area.

Table 8.1. *Strategy and recommendation for future use*

Under favourable conditions knowing the number of tents present can be used to make rough estimates of the number of people residing within a camp area. During the Enviref project counting the number of tents and small houses inside the Beldangi refugee settlements in Nepal, and the Dagahaley and Ifo refugee settlements in Kenya has been done successfully using very-high resolution images from the IKONOS satellite. This number has then been used to estimate the approximate amount of affected people living in the camp. Thus, the use of very high-resolution satellite images may be a significant contribution towards better estimates of the number of people affected during the first stages of a crisis. Aided by detailed field registrations from the camps we have also been able to delineate other important details within the camp, such as larger buildings hosting hospitals, schools,

administration, police etc, in addition to water sites and wells, petrol pumps, and roads and footpaths of various size. IKONOS images also have the potential to be used for detailed refugee camp planning and assessments of environmental changes.

The decision whether or not to invest in remotely sensed imagery depends on what geographic information is already locally available, budgetary constraints, and the required time frame for when information is needed. For most applications, satellite imagery can provide information more quickly than aerial surveys, unless planes and pilots are already available locally.

Very high-resolution satellite imagery is in most cases preferable to aerial photography, both from a cost and benefit perspective, especially for smaller-area coverage such as refugee camps. However, if low-cost paper copies of aerial photographs can be obtained, e.g. through a local university or company, these can also serve as a useful purpose.

We find that by providing fast access to general thematic information over a larger region the LANDSAT-7 ETM+ sensor could be a valuable data source for the relief community, also due to both the global data archive and the low price of only USD600 pr. image.

For performing more detailed analysis, which is especially needed at a later stage of a crisis situation, images at a resolution available e.g. from the IKONOS sensor is needed.